

ADDITIONAL INFORMATION

Speciation chart of indium over the full pH range

Figure a2. Speciation chart of indium at a concentration of 1 μM . The speciation chart is created with CHEAQS Next software version 2014.0.9.4. Input values for the concentration of both indium and chloride are 1×10^{-6} M, and for each pH the regarding H^+ input value has been set as free activity, the concentration of all other elements has been set to 0 M for this evaluation.